

Universität
Basel

Philosophisch-Historische
Fakultät

Profilbereich Osteuropa

Women Writers and the Construction of National Identities in the Long 19th Century

Comparative Perspectives

Thursday, 10.04.- Friday, 11.04.2025
University of Basel

Swiss National
Science Foundation

Ukrainian Research
in Switzerland

Women Writers and the Construction of National Identities in the Long 19th Century

Situated at the crossroads of women's studies and imperial studies, this highly innovative and ambitious scientific event aims to answer the following guiding questions: is not women's subordination to men inherent in the patriarchal conception of the social body made even more suffocating when empires peripheralise ethnic groups, forcing women to fight both for their own rights and for the rights of their nation and culture? And, beyond the history of women's rights, should women who have contributed to the progress of democracy and the cultural emancipation of their countries not be brought out of the shadows? To answer these questions, we will start from the long 19th century, considered as the age of the invention of national identities, and we will see how this movement of intertwining of discourses for national self-determination and struggles for the moral and cultural sovereignty of women continues in the 20th century. This will also be an opportunity to discuss the relevance of the periodicity of this division into centuries.

Zoom

Click this [link](#) or enter the following information manually to be able to watch the workshop. It will be possible to participate passively (neither the activation of the camera nor audio will be possible) in the workshop.

Meeting ID: 655 4484 7386 Access Code: 119065

Send an email to osteuropa-geschichte@unibas.ch should you have problems connecting to the meeting.

Organization

Dr. Nikol Dziub (Basel), Prof. Dr. F. Benjamin Schenk (Basel), Dr. Anna Hodel (Basel)

Support

This workshop was made possible with the help of the Swiss National Science Foundation, Ukrainian Research in Switzerland (URIS), the Profilbereich Osteuropa and the Albrecht'sche Reisefonds of the University of Basel.

Assistance

Dr. Augustin Voegele, Oliver Göhler, Micha Steiner

Program

Day 1 - 10. April 2025

Europainstitut, Riehenstrasse 154, Raum A 3911

- 09:15** **Welcome and introduction**
Nikol Dziub, Anna Hodel, F. Benjamin Schenk (Basel)
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- 09:30-10:30** **Keynote address by Agatha Schwartz** (Ottawa, Canada)
«Negotiating Sisterhood Across National Boundaries: Lessons Learned from the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy»
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- 10:30-11:00** Coffee Break
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- 11:00-12:00** **Panel 1: National Women Writers**
Lena Magnone (Lyon, France)
«Women as National Writers: A Central-European Appendix to *La Fabrique de l'écrivain national*»
Nikol Dziub (Basel)
«*The Ukrainian Paradigm: Lesya Ukrainka between History and Imagination*»
Chair: Anna Hodel
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- 12:00-14:00** Lunch
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- 14:00-15:00** **Panel 2: Women Writers and Nation-Building**
Alla Shvec (Lviv, Ukraine)
«'In the Name of Our National Unity': the Tradition and Significance of Women's Writing in the Nation-Building Processes of Ukraine»
Sylvie Marchenoir (Dijon, France)
«German Nation-Building and Women's Emancipation in the Writings of German Women Writers from 1840 to 1918»
Chair: Agatha Schwartz
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- 15:00-15:20** Coffee Break
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15:20-15:45

Round-table (moderated by Nikol Dziub): Democracy and Women Voices

With 2022 Nobel Peace Prize winner **Oleksandra Matviichuk**, Center for Civil Liberties, Kyjiv, and **Slava Svitova**, Co-Founder and CEO at Creative Women Publishing.

15:50-16:50

Panel 3: Women's Writing and Imperial Identities

F. Benjamin Schenk (Basel)

«The Empire - a Men's Project? Markers of Imperial Identity in Female Autobiographical Writing of Russian Noblewomen (Late 19th Century)»

Catherine Géry (INALCO, Paris, France) (*online*)

«The 'New Woman' in the Imperial Context: *Grandeur* and Misery of a Russian Notion»

Chair: Nikol Dziub

16:50-17:00

Concluding Remarks

Day 2 - 11. April 2025

Universität Basel, Kollegienhaus, Petersplatz 1

Mehrzweckraum 035

09:00-10:00

Panel 4: Women Writers and the Mapping of Identities

Susan Layton (Paris, France)

«A Feminist Deviation from Russian Imperialist Nationalism: Evodkia Rostopchina's Allegory of the Rape of Poland»

Falestin Naili (Basel)

«Fadwa Tuqan: the Mountainous Journey of a Palestinian Poet of the 20th Century»

Chair: Marion Schulze

10:00-10:20

Coffee Break

10:20-12:00	<p>Panel 5: Feminists and National Storytelling</p> <p>Marion Schulze (Basel) «Modernity Stitched. Feminist Storying of 19th-Century Britain»</p> <p>Elena Gueorguieva (Paris, France) «Out of Focus: The Marginalization of Women Writers in Discourses Shaping Bulgarian National Identity»</p> <p>Kateryna Tarasiuk (Strasbourg, France) «Revisiting <i>The First Garland</i>: The Significance of the Feminist Almanac for Today's Women's Movement in Ukraine»</p> <p>Chair: Olena Palko</p>
12:00-14:00	Lunch
14:00-15:30	<p>Panel 6: Women Writers and the Norms of Identity</p> <p>Yvonne Pörzgen (Bochum, Germany) «The Pillars of Society: Gender, Ethnicity and Social Status in Gabriela Zapolska's Novels»</p> <p>Anna Hodel (Basel) «Feminism, Transnationalism and the Mountains: Climbing and Foresight in the Illyrian works of Dragojla Jarnević»</p> <p>Philine Bickhardt (Zurich) «<i>Othering</i> and Orientalism in Jelena Dimitrijević's Travel Writing»</p> <p>Chair: Lena Magnone</p>
15:30-15:50	Coffee Break
15:50-16:00	Concluding Remarks
17:00	City walking tour for participants
